

SPECIES COMPOSITION OF HALOXYLON PESTS.

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada Janubiy Orol buyi saksovul zararkunandalari tur tarkibi buyicha ma'lumotlar berilgan. Tadqiqotlarimiz natijasida: 8 turkumga mansub 243 tur: Termitlar (Isoptera) turkumi – 1, To'g'riqanotlilar (Orthoptera) turkumi – 28, Tripslar (Thysanoptera) turkumi – 1, Tengqanotlilar (Homoptera) turkumi – 16, YArimqattiqanotlilar yoki qandalalar (Heteroptera) turkumi – 7, Qattiqanotlilar yoki qo'ng'izlar (Coleoptera) turkumi – 120, Ikkiqanotlilar (Diptera) turkumi – 17, Tangaqanotlilar yoki kapalaklar (Lepidoptera) turkumi - 53 tur ruyxatga olindi.

Kalit so'zlar: saksovul, zararkunanda, hasharot, qo'ng'izlar, kapalaklar, shiralar, tripslar, chirildoqlar, chigirtkalar, saratonlar, pashshalar, termitlar.

Аннотация. В статье приведены данные по видовому составу насекомых вредителей саксаулового леса Южного Приаралья. В результате наших исследований зарегистрировано 243 видов, относящихся к 8 отрядам: Термиты (Isoptera) – 1, Прямокрылые (Orthoptera) – 28, Трипсы (Thysanoptera) - 1, Равнокрылые (Homoptera) - 16, Полужесткокрылые или клопы (Heteroptera) – 7, Жесткокрылые или жуки - 120, Двукрылые (Diptera) - 17, Чешуекрылые или бабочки (Lepidoptera) - 53 вид.

Ключевые слова: саксаул, вредители, насекомые, жуки, бабочки, тли, трипсы, сверчки, саранчи, цикады, мухи, термиты.

Abstract. The article provides data on the species composition of insect pests in the saxaul forest of the Southern Aral Sea region. As a result of our research, 243 species were registered, belonging to 8 orders: Termites (Isoptera) – 1, Orthoptera – 28, Thysanoptera - 1, Homoptera - 16, Heteroptera - 7, Coleoptera - 120, Diptera - 17, Lepidoptera - 53 species.

Keywords: saxaul, pests, insects, beetles, butterflies, aphids, thrips, crickets, locusts, cicadas, flies, termites.

1. INTRODUCTION. Haloxyton is a plant in the form of a tree growing in the desert, belonging to the Chenopodioideae family. Haloxyton is of great importance in the national economy. It is mainly used as firewood, nutritious fodder for sheep and camels, sand stabilizer and wind breaker. Haloxyton forests play an important role in protecting the soil from erosion. Haloxyton lives 50-60 years. Basically, it grows from seed and starts normal seeding in 5-7 years. As soon as it gets cold, Haloxyton shed their leaves. With the arrival of spring, Haloxyton trees are covered with small flowers. Haloxyton seeds are produced by autumn.

It can be found mainly in Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, as well as China, Iran, and Afghanistan. [1].

There are mainly 3 types of saxophones: Haloxyton aphyllum I., Haloxyton persicum B., and Haloxyton ammodendron B. Since 80% of our region consists of sand dunes, the service of Haloxyton to block the sands is very important. [2].

According to the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 15, 2019 "On measures to accelerate the establishment of "green covers" - protective forests in the dry areas at the bottom of the Aral Sea", rising sand, salt and in order to reduce the negative impact of dust particles, to effectively organize the establishment of forests protecting desert plants in these areas, and to mitigate the negative impact of global climate changes, the

drying up of the Aral Sea, on the development of agriculture and the life of the population. several things are being done.

Taking into account the many useful aspects of Haloxylon, protecting it from harmful insects is relevant today. Research in this direction has not been conducted in Karakalpakstan.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS. Our research was conducted on the basis of generally accepted entomological methods. In the process of catching insects, the traditional method of entomological catching nets and insect traps was used.

Our research on the study of the Haloxylon entomofauna species composition, bioecological features, dynamics of seasonal numbers in the years 2012-2023 was carried out in the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. As a result of our research, 243 species were registered, belonging to 8 orders: Termites (Isoptera) – 1, Orthoptera – 28, Thysanoptera - 1, Homoptera - 16, Heteroptera - 7, Coleoptera - 120, Diptera - 17, Lepidoptera - 53 species.

Species composition of saxovul (Haloxylon) pests in the conditions of Karakalpakstan

	Species name	Harmful organs	Meeting
Isoptera			
1.	<i>Anacanthotermes ahngerianus</i> Jacobs.	stem	+
Orthoptera			
Grylloidae			
2.	<i>Velarifictorus bolivari</i> (Uv)	leaf	+
Pyrgomorphidae			
3.	<i>Pyrgomorpha bispinosa deserti</i>	leaf	+
Pamphagidae			
4.	<i>Thrinchus desertus</i> B.-Bien.	leaf	+
5.	<i>Strumiger desertorum desertorum</i> Zub.	leaf	+
Acrididae			
6.	<i>Dericorys albidula</i> Serv.	leaf	+++
7.	<i>Dericorys annulata roseipennis</i>	leaf	+++
8.	<i>Anacridium aegyptium</i>	leaf	+
9.	<i>Calliptamus turanicus</i>	leaf	+
10.	<i>Calliptamus barbarus cephalotes</i>	leaf	+
11.	<i>Heteracris littoralis littoralis</i>	leaf	+
12.	<i>Heteracris adspersa</i>	leaf	+
13.	<i>Egnatius apicalis</i> Stal	leaf	+
14.	<i>Ochrilidia hebetata kazaka</i>	leaf	+
15.	<i>Locusta migratoria migratoria</i> L.	leaf	+
16.	<i>Acrotylus insubricus</i> (Scop.)	leaf	+
17.	<i>Sphingonotus nebulosus</i>	leaf	+
18.	<i>Sphingonotus octofasciatus</i>	leaf	+
19.	<i>Sphingonotus maculatus maculatus</i>	leaf	+
20.	<i>Sphingonotus carinatus</i>	leaf	+
21.	<i>Pseudoshingonotus.savignyi</i> Sauss.	leaf	+

22	<i>Helioscirtus moseri</i> Sauss.	leaf	+
23	<i>Leptoternis iliensis</i> Uv.	leaf	+
24	<i>Leptoternis gracilis</i> (Ev.)	leaf	+
25	<i>Dociostaurus tartarus</i> Uv.	leaf	+
26	<i>Notostauru salbicornis</i> (Ev.)	leaf	+
27	<i>Notostaurus albicornis turcmenus</i> (Uv.)	leaf	+
28	<i>Eremippus simplex simplex</i> (Ev.)	leaf	+
29	<i>Eremippus comatus</i> Mistsh.	leaf	+
Thysanoptera			
30	<i>Haplothrips arthropityi</i> J.		+++
Homoptera			
31	<i>Cicadatra querula</i> Pall.	leaf	+++
32	<i>Cicadatra ochreate</i> Mel.	leaf	+++
33	<i>Adelungia calligoni</i> Osch.	leaf	+++
34	<i>Achrus albicosta</i>	leaf	+++
35	<i>Achrus nigronervosus</i>	leaf	+++
36	<i>Achrus robustus</i> Hpt.	leaf	+++
37	<i>Cicadatra guerula</i>	leaf	+++
38	<i>Caillardia azurea</i> Log.	leaf	+++
39	<i>Caillardia robusta</i> Log.	leaf	+++
40	<i>Caillardia notata</i> Log.	leaf	+++
41	<i>C.nana</i> L.	leaf	+++
42	<i>Xerophilophis (Brachyunguis) saxaulica.</i>	leaf	+++
43	<i>Schizotargina arthropityi</i> Arch.	leaf	+++
44	<i>Acanthococcus arthropityi</i> Borchs.	leaf	+++
45	<i>Acantholecanium haloxyloni</i> Hall.	leaf	+++
46	<i>Phenacoccus arthropityi</i> Arch.	leaf	+++
Heteroptera			
47	<i>Tarisa fraudatrix</i> Horv.	leaf	+
48	<i>T.elevata</i> R.	leaf	+
49	<i>T.virescens</i> H.S.	leaf	+
50	<i>Brachynema germari</i>	leaf	+
51	<i>Brachynema virens</i> Klug.	leaf	+
52	<i>Lygus kalmi</i>	leaf	+
53	<i>Dolycoris penicellatus</i>	leaf	+
Coleoptera			
Scarabaeidae			
54	<i>Brenskea coronata</i> R.	stem	+
55	<i>B.varentzovi</i> S.	stem	+
56	<i>Chironitis moeris</i> P.	stem	+
57	<i>Anomala</i> sp.	stem	+
58	<i>Chioneosoma kisilkumensis</i> S.	stem	+
59	<i>Chineosoma komarovi</i> F.	stem	+

60.	<i>Chioneosoma tschitscherini</i> Sem.	stem	+
61.	<i>Chioneosoma tschitscherini</i> Sem.	stem	+
62.	<i>Chioneosoma porosum</i> Fisch.	stem	+
63.	<i>Stalagmopygus albella</i>	stem	+
64.	<i>Adoretus nigrifrons</i> Stev.	stem	+
65.	<i>Lethrus rosmarus</i> Ball.	stem	+
66.	<i>Oryctes punctipennis punctipennis</i> Motsch.	stem	+
Tenebrionidae			
67.	<i>Sarathropus fallax</i> L.,	stem	+
68.	<i>S.depressus</i> Z.,	stem	+
69.	<i>Pisterotarsa gigantea</i> F.,	stem	+
70.	<i>Hedyphanes coerulescens</i> ,	stem	+
71.	<i>Diesia sexdentata</i> F.,	stem	+
72.	<i>Pimelia verrucosa</i> ,	stem	+
73.	<i>P.cephalotes</i> ,	stem	+
74.	<i>Tagona macrophtalma</i> F.,	stem	+
75.	<i>Trachyderma triangularis</i> F.,	stem	+
76.	<i>Adesmia gebleri</i> ,	stem	+
77.	<i>Podhamala acuta</i> F.,	stem	+
78.	<i>Trigonoscelis nodosa</i> F.,	stem	+
79.	<i>Sphenaria karelini</i> M.,	stem	+
80.	<i>Cyphostethe komarovi</i> R.,	stem	+
81.	<i>Colposphaena karelini</i> M.,	stem	+
82.	<i>C.brevicollis</i> S.,	stem	+
83.	<i>Leptoaphsena rubriceps</i> R.,	stem	+
84.	<i>Psammocryptus minutus intermedius</i> B.,	stem	+
85.	<i>C.karelini</i> ,	stem	+
86.	<i>Oogaster piceus subsp.lehmanni</i> M.	stem	+
87.	<i>Tentyria gigas</i> Fald.	stem	+
88.	<i>Ocnera pilicollis</i> Fald.	stem	+
89.	<i>Blaps heophila</i> F.-W.	stem	+
90.	<i>Blaps parvicollis subcordata</i> Seidl.	stem	+
Buprestidae			
91.	<i>Julodis variolaris</i> ,	stem	+
92.	<i>Julodis variolaris bucharica</i> Sem.,	stem	+
93.	<i>Sphenoptera parfentjevi</i> Step.,	stem	+
94.	<i>Sphenoptera potanini</i> B. Jak.,	stem	+
95.	<i>Sphenoptera hauseri</i> (Reitter, 1895),	stem	+
96.	<i>Sphenoptera ignita</i> (Reitter, 1895),	stem	+
97.	<i>Sphenoptera striatipennis</i> (Yakowlew, 1885),	stem	+
98.	<i>Sphenoptera punctatissima</i> (Reitter, 1895),	stem	+
99.	<i>Sympiezocnemis gigantea</i> F. – W.,	stem	+
100.	<i>Trigonoscelis grandis</i> F.,	stem	+

10	<i>Sternodes caspicus</i> ,	stem	+
10	<i>Turcmenigena varentzovi</i> Melg.),	stem	+
10	<i>Ischyronota conicicollis</i> Weise.,	stem	+
10	<i>Corigetetus exquisitus</i> Fst.,	stem	+
10	<i>Leucochromus imperialis</i> Zubk.,	stem	+
10	<i>Chromosomus fischeri</i> Fahrs.,	stem	+
10	<i>Capnodis excise</i> Men.,	stem	+
10	<i>Anthaxia stepanovi</i> Richt.,	stem	+
10	<i>Acmaeoderella personata</i> (Semenov, 1896)	stem	+
11	<i>Lampetis argentata</i> Mnnh.	stem	+
Meloidae			
11	<i>Cerocoma scafferi</i> L.	leaf	+
11	<i>Mylabris elegantissima</i> Zubk.	leaf	+
11	<i>Mylabris tekkensis</i> Heyd.	leaf	+
11	<i>Mylabris triangulifera</i> Heyd.	leaf	+
11	<i>Mylabris scabiosae</i> Ol.	leaf	+
11	<i>Mylabris cyaneovaria</i> Rtt.	leaf	+
11	<i>Mylabris coerulescens</i> Gebl.	leaf	+
11	<i>Mylabris magnogutata</i> (Heyd.)	leaf	+
11	<i>M.schrenkei</i> G.	leaf	+
12	<i>M.sedecimpunctata</i> G.	leaf	+
12	<i>Mylabris frolovi</i> Germ.	leaf	+
12	<i>Mylabris quadripunctata</i> L.	leaf	+
12	<i>Lytta coccinea</i> M.	leaf	+
12	<i>Zonitis flava</i> F.	leaf	+
12	<i>Z.bipunctata</i> G.	leaf	+
12	<i>Hycleus scabiosae</i> (Olivier)	leaf	+
12	<i>Rhampholyssa steveni</i> W.	leaf	+
Cerambycidae			
12	<i>Prionus turkestanicus</i> S.	stem	+
12	<i>Turcmenigena varentzovi</i> Melg.	stem	+
13	<i>Turcmenigena varentzovi</i> Melg.	stem	+
13	<i>Mesoprionus komarovi</i> (Dobrn)	stem	+
13	<i>Placaederus scapularis</i>	stem	+
Chrysomelidae			
13	<i>Antipa silensis</i> W.	leaf	+
13	<i>Cryptocephalus samargentus</i> F.	leaf	+
13	<i>Ischyronota conicicollis</i> W.	leaf	+
13	<i>Ischyronota conicicollis</i> W.	leaf	+
13	<i>Nyctiphanthus hirtus</i> S.	leaf	+
13	<i>Chrysolina sacarum</i>	leaf	+
13	<i>Aphilenia parvula</i> W.	leaf	+
14	<i>Collaphellus hoefti</i> M.	leaf	+

14	<i>Phyllotreta pallidipennis</i> R.	leaf	+
14	<i>Stephanophorus verrucosus</i>	leaf	+
14	<i>Lepidotychius morawitzi</i> B.	leaf	+
14	<i>Chloebius latifrons</i> F.	leaf	+
14	<i>Ch.sterbai</i> R.	leaf	+
14	<i>Sitonia cylindricollis</i> F.	leaf	+
14	<i>Megamecus variegatus</i>	leaf	+
14	<i>Chromonotus vittatus</i>	leaf	+
14	<i>Parastylus truchmenus</i> F.	leaf	+
15	<i>Chromoderus fasciatus</i> M.	leaf	+
15	<i>Brachycleonus fronto</i>	leaf	+
15	<i>Ammocleonus quadrimaculatus</i> M.	leaf	+
15	<i>Theone costipennis</i> Kirsch.	leaf	+
Curculionidae			
15	<i>Lixus flavescens</i>	branch	+
15	<i>L.kraatzi</i>	branch	+
15	<i>L.desertorum</i> G.	branch	+
15	<i>L.astrachanicus</i>	branch	+
15	<i>L.strangulatus</i> F.	branch	+
15	<i>L.algirus</i>	branch	+
16	<i>Coniatus steveni</i> C.	branch	+
16	<i>Elasmobaris alboguttatus</i> F.	branch	+
16	<i>Myllocerus benignus</i> F.	branch	+
16	<i>Corigetetus exquisitus</i> Fst.	branch	+
16	<i>Leucochromus imperialis</i> Zubk.	branch	+
16	<i>Chromosomus fischeri</i> Fahrs.	branch	+
16	<i>Platymycterus trapezicollis</i> B.	branch	+
16	<i>Megamecus variegatus</i> Gebl.	branch	+
16	<i>Baris memnonia</i> Boh.	branch	+
Elateridae			
16	<i>Agriotes meticulosus</i> Cand	branch	+
17	<i>Agriotes caspicus</i> Heyd.	branch	+
17	<i>Aeoloides grisescens</i> Germ.	branch	+
17	<i>Drasterius bimaculatus</i> Rossi.	branch	+
17	<i>Melanotus acuminatus</i> Rtt.	branch	+
17	<i>Cardiophorus longulus</i> Er.	branch	+
Diptera			
Cecidomyiidae			
17	<i>Haloxylonomyia gigas</i> Marik.	branch	+
17	<i>Haloxylonomyia furtiva</i> Marik.	branch	+
17	<i>Asiodiplosis noxia</i> Marik.	branch	+
17	<i>Asiodiplosis meridianus</i> Marik.	branch	+
17	<i>Asiodiplosis ulkunkalkani</i> Marik.	branch	+

18	<i>Asiodiplosis stackelbergi</i> Marik.	branch	+
18	<i>Baldratia przewalskii</i> Marik.	branch	+
18	<i>Stefaniola gigas</i> M.	branch	+
18	<i>St.congregata</i> M.	branch	+
18	<i>St.deformans</i> M.	branch	+
18	<i>Asiodiplosis ulkunkalkani</i> M.	branch	+
18	<i>A.meridianus</i> M.	branch	+
18	<i>Baldartia kozlovi</i> M.	branch	+
18	<i>B.przevalskii</i> M.	branch	+
18	<i>Haloxylaphaga infestans</i> M.	branch	+
19	<i>Ariodofavilla bicuspidata</i> M.	branch	+
Xylophagidae			
19	<i>Erinna</i> sp.		+
Lepidoptera			
Cossidae			
19	<i>Holcocerus campicola</i> Ev.	leaf	+
19	<i>H.insperus</i> Ch.	leaf	+
19	<i>H.glareosa</i>	leaf	+
Tortricidae			
19	<i>Hysterosia subfumida</i> Flkv.	seed	+
Coleophoridae			
19	<i>Characia haloxyli</i> Flkv.	bud	+++
19	<i>Casignetella gallivora</i> Flkv.	bud	+++
19	<i>Coleophora saxauli</i> F.		+++
Scythrididae			
19	<i>Scythrus cirra</i> Flkv.	bud	+++
20	<i>Scythrus haloxylella</i> Flkv.	bud	+++
Gelechidae			
20	<i>Scrobipalpa</i> sp.2	leaf	+++
Pyralidae			
20	<i>Anoristia atrisparsella</i> Rag.	bud	+++
Sphingidae			
20	<i>Celerio lineata</i> Esp.	bud	+++
20	<i>Deilephila lineata</i> Esp.	bud	+++
Zygaenidae			
20	<i>Zygaena truchmena</i> Ev.	leaf	+++
Geometridae			
20	<i>Paraphthorarcha kasachstanika</i> Stsh.	bud	+++
Lasiocampidae			
20	<i>Lasiocampa eversmanni</i> Ev.	leaf	+++
Arctiidae			
20	<i>Lacydes spectabiis</i> Tausch.	leaf, bud	+++
20	<i>Tanera pardalina</i> Pungl.	leaf, bud	+++

21	<i>Phragmatobia fuliginosa</i> L.	leaf	+
21	<i>Arctia caja</i> L.	leaf	+
Orguidae			
21	<i>Orgyia dubia</i> Tausch.	Seed, leaf, bud	+++
Noctuidae			
21	<i>Euxoa conspicua</i> Hb.	Seed, bud	+++
21	<i>Carderia ptotchica</i> Pungl.	Seed, bud	+++
21	<i>Carderia irrissor</i> Er.	Seed, bud	+++
21	<i>Carderia sociabilis</i> Grasl.	Seed, bud	+++
21	<i>Polia ptotchica</i> Pungl.	Seed, bud	+++
21	<i>Thargella fissilus</i> Chr.	leaf, bud	+++
21	<i>T.sitiens</i> Pungl.	leaf, bud	+++
22	<i>Pseudohadena chenopodiphaga</i> Rmb.	Seed, bud	+++
22	<i>Pseudohadena siri</i> E.	leaf	+++
22	<i>P.immunda</i> Ev.	leaf, bud	+++
22	<i>P.immunus</i> Stgr.	leaf, bud	+++
22	<i>P.siri</i> Ersh.	leaf, bud	+++
22	<i>Athetis albino</i> Ev.	bud	+++
22	<i>A.guadripunctata</i> F.	bud	+++
22	<i>Diadochia esurialis</i> Pungl.	bud	+++
22	<i>D.malitosa</i> Alph.	bud	+++
22	<i>Jaxartia elinguis</i> Pungl.	leaf	+++
23	<i>J.striolata</i> Fill.	bud	+++
23	<i>Odantelia distincta</i> Chr.	leaf	+++
23	<i>Odontelia arenicola</i> S.,	leaf	+++
23	<i>Odontelia fissilis</i> C.	leaf	+++
23	<i>Scythcentropus scipturosa</i> Ev.	seed	+++
23	<i>Clytie syriaca</i> B.	leaf	+
23	<i>Discestra cociabilis</i> G.	leaf	+
23	<i>Hadula sabulorum</i> A.	leaf	+
23	<i>Cucullia boryphora</i> F.-W	leaf	+
23	<i>Aleucanitis flexuosa</i> Men.	leaf	+
Pieridae			
24	<i>Colias erate</i> Esp.	leaf	+
24	<i>Zegris fausti</i> Chr.	leaf	+
Lycaenidae			
24	<i>Lycaena icarus</i> Rtt.	leaf	+
Nymphalidae			
24	<i>Pyrameis cardui</i> L.	leaf	+

Reminder:

«+++» - common species

«+» - rare species

4. CONCLUSION. As a result of our research, 243 species were registered, belonging to 8 orders: Termites (Isoptera) – 1, Orthoptera – 28, Thysanoptera - 1, Homoptera - 16, Heteroptera - 7, Coleoptera - 120, Diptera - 17, Lepidoptera - 53 species.

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